

On the Business Analyst's Responsibilities in an Agile Software Project - a Multi-Method Study

Mateusz Kwiatkowski

Department of Software Engineering;
Gdańsk University of Technology
Gdańsk, Poland

s174159@student.pg.edu.pl

Aleksander Jarzębowicz

Department of Software Engineering;
Gdańsk University of Technology
Gdańsk, Poland

olek@eti.pg.edu.pl

1. Introduction

This report provides more details on results of a questionnaire-based survey with IT practitioners, dedicated to the responsibilities assigned to business analysts in the organizations the respondents work for.

This document should be considered an appendix to the paper published at the 32nd International Conference on Information Systems Development (ISD 2024). Due to the limited number of pages, the details could not be included in the paper.

2. Respondents' Demographics

This section presents the responses to demographic questions.

What is your job position?

72 responses

Fig. 1. Job position.

What is your experience in this job position?

72 responses

Fig. 2. Job experience.

What is your experience with agile methodologies?

72 responses

Fig. 3. Agile experience.

Which agile methodologies are used in your company?

72 responses

Fig. 4. Agile methodologies used.

What is the size of the company you work for?

72 responses

Fig. 5. Size of the company

What is your company domain?

72 responses

Fig. 6. Business domain/sector.

Does your company have a person in the position called "Business Analyst" or maybe an employee in a position with a different name performs duties related to business analysis?

72 responses

Fig. 7. Naming of business analyst position.

3. Responses to Questions About BA’s Responsibilities

This section presents the responses to the main questions of the survey i.e. questions about business analyst’s responsibilities in respondent’s organization. All questions were multiple-choice closed questions. They are presented according to the same structure that was used in the questionnaire (divided into 7 work areas).

3.1. Product Backlog Area

Responsibilities	% of responses	No. of responses
R1: Managing the Product Backlog	72,2%	52
R2: Accepting User Stories to the PB	55,6%	40
R3: Refining the Product Backlog	77,8%	56
R5: Prioritizing the Product Backlog	45,8%	33

Fig. 8. Distribution of responses on Product Backlog-related responsibilities.

3.2. Requirements Area

Responsibilities	% of responses	No. of responses
R6: Analyzing Use Cases	76,4%	55
R7: Gathering requirements	88,9%	64
R8: Prioritizing requirements	55,6%	40
R9: Creating User Stories	75,0%	54
R10: Documenting requirements	91,7%	66
R13: Explaining requirements to developers	81,9%	59
R14: Requirements refinement	83,3%	60
R15: Acceptance test criteria definition	66,7%	48
R16: Creating epics	54,2%	39
R18: Collaboration with stakeholders	84,7%	61

Fig. 9. Distribution of responses on Requirements-related responsibilities.

3.3. Project Area

Responsibilities	% of responses	No. of responses
R24: Release management	27,8%	20
R25: Managing the project	12,5%	9
R27: Risk assessment	34,7%	25
R29: Tracking status of the project	44,4%	32
R34: Adding project tasks to Jira	75,0%	54

Fig. 10. Distribution of responses on Project-related responsibilities.

3.4. Product Area

Responsibilities	% of responses	No. of responses
R36: Maximizing value of the product	61,1%	44
R37: Developing product vision	26,4%	19
R40: Being ahead and working on the next product's version	45,8%	33
R41: Analyzing the product	68,1%	49
R42: Providing information for managerial decisions about the product	66,7%	48

Fig. 11. Distribution of responses on Product-related responsibilities.

3.5. Business Area

Responsibilities	% of responses	No. of responses
R43: Business plan development	20,8%	15
R48: User support	40,3%	29
R49: Providing business expertise	40,3%	29
R51: Identifying customers	26,4%	19
R52: Travelling to other company sites	13,9%	10
R55: Identifying business needs	73,6%	53
R58: Communication and sharing vision between stakeholders	51,4%	37
R64: Financial analysis	11,1%	8
R66: Analyzing business needs	83,3%	60

Fig. 12. Distribution of responses on Business-related responsibilities.

3.6. Team Area

Responsibilities	% of responses	No. of responses
R68: Sprint Planning involvement	65,3%	47
R69: Cooperation with teams	80,6%	58
R72: Team leadership	16,7%	12
R73: Daily meetings participation	73,6%	53
R75: Consultations with team members related to product requirements	77,8%	56
R76: Refinement participation	75,0%	54
R77: Participation in demo meetings	72,2%	52
R78: Communication between teams and clients	69,4%	50
R79: Support for Product Owner	80,6%	58
R80: Technical support for team members	31,9%	23

Fig. 13. Distribution of responses on Team-related responsibilities.

3.7. Development Area

Responsibilities	% of responses	No. of responses
R85: Implementing	15,3%	11
R86: Acceptance testing	48,6%	35
R87: Verification testing	55,6%	40
R89: Merging code changes after passed tests	6,9%	5

Fig. 14. Distribution of responses on Development-related responsibilities.